

ENHANCING AFFECTIVE COMMITMENT IN SPEAKING THROUGH PUBLIC SERVICE MOTIVATION

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Abstract

This research examines the dynamics of the behaviour of State Civil Apparatus (ASN) employees in the Immigration Office of East Java within the context of organizational change. Using a quantitative approach and SEM-AMOS analysis, the total sample in this study consisted of 196 respondents selected through proportional random sampling. Therefore, interesting findings were that Public Service Motivation could affect Affective Commitment to Change only through full mediation of Voice Behaviour, while Relational Crafting can affect it directly and through partial mediation. Surprisingly, Superficial Harmony weakens the effect of both on Voice Behaviour. This finding underlines the importance of employee voice behaviour facilitated by organizations in their relational crafting by reducing superficial harmony that can inhibit the expression of employees. This study contributes significantly to an understanding of the dynamics of organizational change in the public sector, especially in the context of immigration services in Indonesia.

Keywords: Leadership, Motivation, Organizational Change, Public Sector, Service.

1. INTRODUCTION

Organizational change is inevitable, whether it comes from external factors such as demands and expectations of society, or internal to the organization such as the need to develop. In facing change, the involvement and support of human resources (HR) are the keys to success. Not every employee may be willing to support change, while some even refuse to accept the change. This may negatively affect organizational performance.

Congruence theory refers to the degree at which an individual perceives a good fit between that person and their environment. For organizational change to be supported by employees, there has to be congruence on the part of employees with the environment that will support change. Two factors influencing this level of fit are public service motivation and employee willingness to voluntarily relate to others-relation crafting.

Public service motivation can be defined as the motivation of employees in providing the best service for the public's interest even by setting aside personal interests. Perhaps the motivation of public service may influence employees to give out their affective commitment to change, as evidenced in some prior researches of Saryono et al. (2022); Aini (2002) and Rofcanin et al. (2019).

On the other hand, contradictory research can also be found where changes running counter to the motivation values of employees within public service will fail to create a strongly affective commitment. According to Bozeman & Su (2015) and Kotlarsky & Oshri (2005).

On the other hand, relational crafting refers to employees' efforts to manage interpersonal relationships in the workplace voluntarily. Results from previous studies indicated that relational crafting may lead to an increase in the voluntary behaviour of employees to voice their ideas and suggestions (voice behaviour) (Hamid & Earlyanti, 2023; Yudiatmaja, 2019) and increase the affective commitment to change (Tian et al., 2022).

Voice behaviour can serve as a mediator in the connection between public service motivation, relational crafting, and affective commitment to change. Employees who exhibit elevated levels of public service motivation and engage in relational crafting are often more proactive in expressing ideas for enhancement, which may reinforce their emotional commitment to change.

However, in a work environment that has a strong "superficial harmony" culture, where employees tend to avoid conflict and prioritize apparent harmony, employee voice behaviour can be hampered. In this situation, employees are reluctant to express problems or differences of opinion for fear of disrupting the harmony that has been established. Therefore, superficial harmony can weaken the influence of public service motivation and relational crafting on voice behaviour.

This study seeks to examine the mediating influence of voice behaviour and the moderating effect of superficial harmony in elucidating the relationship among public service motivation, relational crafting, and affective commitment to change, as outlined in the preceding description. This study was conducted on State Civil Apparatus (ASN) at the Immigration Office throughout East Java.

This research aims to offer both theoretical and practical insights. From a theoretical perspective, it seeks to enhance the existing literature on affective commitment to change by incorporating the concepts of self-congruence, public service motivation, relational crafting, voice behaviour, and superficial harmony.

The findings of this study can offer valuable insights for the leaders of the East Java Immigration Office in managing human resources in order to encourage employee affective commitment to change.

Numerous research gaps have been identified in prior studies. Firstly, there exists a lack of consensus in research findings concerning the impact of public service motivation on affective commitment to change. Secondly, the constructs of affective commitment to change, relational crafting, and superficial harmony remain underexplored.

Lastly, the relationship between relational crafting and its effects on voice behaviour and affective commitment to change is a relatively novel area that has not been extensively examined in existing literature.

This research aims to develop a conceptual model that elucidates the connections among public service motivation, relational crafting, voice behaviour, superficial harmony, and affective commitment to change.

Furthermore, it is anticipated that this study will offer empirical evidence concerning the mediating influence of voice behaviour and the moderating effect of superficial harmony within the framework of the East Java Immigration Office in Indonesia.

2. METHODS

This study represents a form of fundamental and causal research, employing a quantitative methodology. The quantitative framework prioritizes the testing of theories by measuring variables through numerical data and conducting statistical analysis.

The design elements to be included in this study are experiments or observations, variable selection, techniques for collecting data, research instrument, data analysis, sample collection, and result reporting.

The population in this study were State Civil Apparatus (ASN) at Immigration Offices throughout East Java, Indonesia who are tasked with providing public services and utilizing Information Technology (IT). The total population was 386 people.

The sample was determined using the Slovin formula with a 5% error rate. The calculation indicated that a total of 196 ASN samples were required. The method employed for sampling was proportional random sampling, which divided the number of samples according to the percentage of ASN at each Immigration office.

This research investigates various key factors that influence the dynamics of ASN employment. Public Service Motivation embodies the drive of ASN to contribute to the community by placing public and communal interests at the forefront, as measured based on indicators from Perry & Vandenberg (2015) and Yudiantmaja (2020).

Next, Relational Crafting describes efforts at social change in the workplace through adjustments to tasks, relationships, and cognitive perspectives, referring to the job crafting dimensions of Berg et al. (2013).

In addition, Affective Commitment to Change refers to a scale that measures how much ASN wants to support the organization's change based on indications by Herscovitch & Meyer (2002), while Voice Behaviour draws on the behaviour of ASN in voicing their innovative ideas or suggestions to improve the organization and covers four main aspects according to (Dyne et al., 2003).

Superficial Harmony: Finally, it reveals efforts toward superficial interpersonal harmony. According to Zhang & Wei (2017), it is measured in terms of five indicators. Since the research instrument for measuring the research variables used a Likert scale, responses were evaluated using a scale from 1, indicating Strongly Disagree, to 5, indicating Strongly Agree.

The questionnaire included both open and closed questions to gather information regarding the identities of the respondents as well as their answers related to the research variables. The data analysis employed Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) utilizing the AMOS (Analysis of Moment Structure) software package, version 29.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Source: Researcher's results (2024)

3. RESULTS

Measurement Model Analysis

The analysis of the measurement model seeks to assess the appropriateness of construct measurement, along with the validity and reliability of the indicators that represent the construct. This analysis is conducted concurrently across all constructs, with the estimation results illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Measurement Model Estimation Results

Source: Researcher's results (2024)

Measurement Model Fit Evaluation

Hair (2010) indicated that evaluating the fit of a measurement model requires the use of at least one absolute fit index alongside an additional index, specifically an incremental fit index. The Goodness of Fit Index (GFI) is commonly employed as the absolute index, while the Comparative Fit Index (CFI) is frequently utilized as the incremental index due to its insensitivity to model complexity. Additionally, parsimony fit indices are not effective for assessing the adequacy of a single model; rather, they are intended for comparing the fit of two or more models. The outcomes of the measurement model fit test, as illustrated in Figure 2, are detailed in Table 1 below.

Table 1: Fit Measure on the Measurement Model

Fit Measure		Critical Value	Fit Measure	
			Index value	Description
Absolute Fit Indices	Prob. χ^2 ^(a)	> 0,05	0,000	Even good fit
	Cmin/df	£ 3,00	1,728	Good fit
	GFI	³ 0,90	0,864	Marginal fit
	RMSEA	£ 0,08	0,061	Good fit
	SRMR	£ 0,08	0,045	Good fit
Incremental FitIndices	CFI	³ 0,95	0,962	Good fit
	TLI	³ 0,94	0,954	Good fit
	NFI	³ 0,90	0,915	Good fit
	RFI	³ 0,90	0,898	Marginal fit
Parsimony Fit Indices (b)	AGFI	³ 0,90	0,822	Marginal fit

^(a) In a model with a sample size of n>250 or more than 25 indicators (m>25), the model is still fit even though the probability value is below 0.05 or is called even a good fit (Hair *et al.*, 2018:584).
^(b) Parsimony fit indices are not used in testing the fit of a single model.

Source: Researcher's results (2024)

The results of the suitability test for the measurement model are presented in Table 1. The findings indicate that both absolute fit indices and incremental fit indices have satisfied the necessary criteria. However, parsimony fit indices were not utilized, as they are primarily intended for comparing the suitability of multiple models rather than assessing a single model. Consequently, the measurement model is deemed acceptable due to its favourable suitability, characterized by both good fit and marginal fit. A good fit signifies that the measurement model demonstrates a high level of model fit, whereas marginal fit suggests that the model's fit remains within acceptable parameters.

Direct Effect Analysis

In the assessment of direct effects, hypothesis testing is conducted to evaluate the significance of the direct relationships between variables, utilizing the critical ratio (CR) and probability value (p-value). The determination of significant direct influence between variables is based on the criterion that if the CR value is greater than or equal to 1.96 or the p-value is less than or equal to the nominal level of 5%, it is concluded that a significant influence exists. Conversely, if the CR value is less than 1.96 or the p-value exceeds the nominal level of 5%, it

is concluded that the influence is insignificant. The subsequent section presents the results of the structural relationship tests aimed at evaluating each research hypothesis based on the output from Structural Equation Modelling (SEM).

Table 2: Testing Structural Relationships between Variables

No	Direct Influence Path	Std. Estimate	S.E. bootstrap	C.R.	P
1	X1 → Z	0,464	0,102	5,010	0,010
2	X1 → Y	0,113	0,091	1,429	0,124
3	X2 → Z	0,532	0,097	5,412	0,009
4	X2 → Y	0,379	0,112	3,491	0,014
5	Z → Y	0,534	0,146	3,822	0,004

Description:
 X1 : Public Service Motivation M : Superficial Harmony
 X2 : Relational Crafting Y : Affective Commitment to Change
 Z : Voice Behaviour

(*)S.E., C.R., and p-value were calculated using the bootstrap bias-corrected percentile method

Source: Researcher's results (2024)

Based on Table 2 above, it can be explained as follows:

- Public Service Motivation (X1) has a significant effect on Voice Behaviours (Z) (CR = 5.010; p = 0.010).
- Public Service Motivation (X1) has an insignificant effect on Affective Commitment to Change (Y) (CR = 1.429; p = 0.124).
- Relational Crafting (X2) has a significant effect on Voice Behaviours (Z) (CR = 5.412; p = 0.009).
- Relational Crafting (X2) has a significant effect on Affective Commitment to Change (Y) (CR = 3.491; p = 0.014).
- Voice Behaviours (Z) has a significant effect on Affective Commitment to Change (Y) (CR = 3.822; p = 0.004).

Indirect Effect Analysis

The results presented below pertain to the analysis of the indirect influence pathway involving public service motivation and relational crafting on affective commitment to change, with voice behaviour serving as a mediating factor. The nature of mediation can be assessed based on its mediating effect. If the direct influence of the exogenous variable on the endogenous variable is significant, and the indirect influence through the mediating variable also demonstrates a significant pathway, this is classified as partial mediation or complementary mediation. Conversely, if the direct influence of the exogenous variable on the endogenous variable is not significant, while the indirect influence through the mediating variable is significant, this is categorized as full mediation or perfect mediation (Zhao et al., 2010).

4. DISCUSSION

The Influence of Public Service Motivation on Voice Behaviour in ASN Immigration Offices throughout East Java, Indonesia

The findings from the SEM analysis indicate that the influence coefficient of public service motivation on voice behaviour is both positive and significant. Consequently, the research hypothesis asserting that public service motivation significantly impacts voice behaviour among ASN Immigration Offices across East Java is validated. This suggests that an increase in the motivation of ASN in public service correlates with an enhancement in their voice behaviour.

The results of this study are in line with the results of research by Boyd & Nowell (2020); Hassan et al. (2021) and Teo et al. (2016), research indicates that there is a direct correlation between public service motivation and the expression of voice behaviour among employees. This earlier investigation has established a positive association between public service motivation and voice behaviour within the realm of public service. Public service motivation is defined as the drive that individuals employed in the public sector, such as those at the Immigration Office, inherently possess, which encourages them to actively participate in their work, provide input, and contribute to organizational improvement.

The underlying rationale for the notable positive correlation between public service motivation and voice behaviour is rooted in the aspiration to enhance public services. Individuals exhibiting elevated levels of public service motivation are generally characterized by a robust commitment to the improvement of public services, they believe that public services must be improved and that positive changes in the organization are needed to achieve these goals. Therefore, they are more likely to provide input and participate in voice behaviour to improve public services (Perry & Vandenabeele, 2015).

Another theoretical support is related to feelings of responsibility for the public interest. Individual employees with high public service motivation also tend to have a strong sense of responsibility for the public interest, they feel they have an important role in maintaining and improving the welfare of society. Therefore, they are more likely to use voice behaviour as a means to ensure that the organization operates in accordance with principles and goals that are oriented towards the public interest (Bright, 2021).

Bozeman & Su (2015), the notable connection between public service motivation and voice behaviour is further linked to the focus on public satisfaction. Employees who possess a high level of public service motivation are inclined to prioritize public satisfaction as the primary objective of their professional endeavours. In an effort to achieve public satisfaction, they will use voice behaviour to identify and fix problems or deficiencies in public services.

The Influence of Relational Crafting on Voice Behaviour in ASN Immigration Offices throughout East Java, Indonesia

The findings from the SEM analysis indicate that the coefficient reflecting the impact of relational crafting on voice behaviour is both positive and significant. Consequently, the

research hypothesis asserting that relational crafting significantly influences voice behaviour in ASN Immigration Offices across East Java is validated. This suggests that an increase in relational crafting correlates with an enhancement in ASN voice behaviour.

The results of this study are in line with the results of research by Hamid & Earlyanti (2023); Yudiantmaja (2019) and Qi & Wang (2018) that high relational crafting will encourage an increase in employee voice behaviour.

In the context of immigration, relational crafting refers to the efforts of individual employees to actively manage their interpersonal relationships at the Immigration Office where they work in a way that enhances collaboration, communication, and positive relationships with co-workers. Relational crafting is rooted in theories that recognize the importance of interpersonal relationships in the workplace, relational crafting also describes individual employee efforts to improve interpersonal relationships in positive ways, such as improving communication, supporting co-workers, and creating a more harmonious work climate.

When employees feel comfortable and have good relationships with co-workers and leaders, they are more likely to be open to voicing their opinions (increased voice behaviour). Effective relational crafting can create an environment that supports voice behaviour because individuals feel more secure, valued, and heard by co-workers and management. Relational crafting can also promote more effective communication in the workplace, which is an important component of voice behaviour, meaning that when employees have good relationships with co-workers, they are more likely to discuss ideas, problems, or needed changes. Increased involvement in these interpersonal relationships can help employees feel more involved in their work overall, which can encourage them to be more active in voice behaviour (Liao et al., 2016).

Relational crafting also influences voice behaviour because of the social support for voice behaviour. Relational crafting can create strong social networks in the workplace, and having good social support can provide encouragement for voice behaviour. When employees feel supported by co-workers and have positive relationships, they are more likely to engage in voice behaviour and feel that their contributions are valued (N. Li et al., 2013). The connection between relational crafting and voice behaviour highlights the significance of fostering positive interpersonal relationships within the workplace. Such relationships are essential for cultivating an environment that encourages open communication, innovation, and active engagement in organizational improvement.

The Influence of Public Service Motivation on Affective Commitment to Change in ASN Immigration Offices throughout East Java, Indonesia

The findings derived from the SEM analysis indicated that the effect of public service motivation on affective commitment to change was negligible. Consequently, the study's hypothesis, which posited a significant difference in the influence of public service motivation on affective commitment to change within ASN Immigration Offices across East Java, is not supported. In essence, although ASN demonstrates a high level of motivation to serve the public, this does not translate into a substantial effect on their affective commitment to change.

This result contradicts several prior studies such as Aini (2002); Rofcanin et al. (2019) and Wang (2021). Those studies concluded that the higher the motivation of ASN in public service, the stronger their affective commitment to making changes. The finding also contradicts the research of Ritz et al. (2016), which discusses motivation for change that is oriented towards the public interest. As stated in the study, public service motivation "should create a strong motivation to participate in changes that have positive impact on public services, which then leads to a strong emotional commitment to make changes that support organizational goals."

Based on the findings of the researcher's review, this anomaly could be corroborated through a number of reasons. There is a lack of congruence between public service motivation values and organizational change at the Immigration Office. According to Bozeman & Su (2015), when organizational change is not aligned with individual public service motivation values, affective commitment to change tends to decrease.

Moreover, the feelings of uncertainty and job security concerns also play a significant role. Organisational changes that often happen in the Immigration Office create anxiety in every employee's mind about their job's future. This concurs with the opinion of Herscovitch & Meyer (2002), who stated that organisational changes happening too frequently can lower individual affective commitment towards the change.

Still, other external factors inhibiting employee affective commitment to change include bureaucratic support for immigration services, which is sometimes provided through ineffective communication and unstable organizational culture. Meyer & Herscovitch (2001) stressed that the influence of such external factors is very strong while the leading role of public service motivation in the development of affective commitment to change cannot always be identified.

In addition, a consideration of the impact of change by individualization is that not all changes in the Immigration Office have an equivalent impact on each ASN individual. According to Oreg (2006) statement, individuals can respond to change differently based on their characteristics, such as the level of public service motivation, the level of work involvement, and other aspects.

Finally, the context and type of change being experienced in the Immigration Office serve as yet another contextual factor that provides less enabling of employee public service motivation to strengthen affective commitment to change. According to Kotlarsky & Oshri (2005), the context and nature of the change may influence the relationship between public service motivation and emotional commitment to change, weakening its potency. Transformational changes, for instance, have different influences compared to incremental changes.

The Influence of Relational Crafting on Affective Commitment to Change in ASN Immigration Offices throughout East Java, Indonesia

The findings from the SEM analysis indicate that the coefficient reflecting the impact of relational crafting on affective commitment to change is both positive and significant. Consequently, the research hypothesis asserting that relational crafting significantly influences

affective commitment to change within ASN Immigration Offices across East Java is validated. This suggests that an increase in relational crafting correlates with a heightened affective commitment of ASN towards change.

The results of this study are in line with the results of the research of Tian et al. (2022); Ali et al. (2020) and S. Li et al. (2022) that high relational crafting will encourage strengthening of affective commitment to change.

Relational crafting refers to an individual's efforts to actively manage and strengthen their interpersonal relationships at the Immigration Office. Good interpersonal relationships are very important because they can influence communication, cooperation, and support in dealing with change. Meanwhile, in the context of Immigration Services, affective commitment to change is the level of emotional commitment of ASN individuals to the changes that occur at the Immigration Office.

The theoretical framework underpinning the positive correlation between relational crafting and affective commitment to change is closely associated with social support and trust. According to Meyer & Herscovitch (2001), relational crafting can foster robust social support within the workplace. This social support plays a crucial role in assisting employees in managing change and feeling adequately supported throughout the process. Additionally, employees who perceive support from their colleagues and maintain positive interpersonal relationships are likely to exhibit elevated levels of affective commitment to impending changes.

Eisenbeiss et al. (2008) added that relational crafting can help employees feel more connected to their organization. When individuals feel that their relationship with the organization is positive, they are more likely to have a high affective commitment to changes initiated by the organization. A strong relationship with the organization can create a sense of shared ownership of the change, which can increase affective commitment to it.

The implication is that by strengthening positive interpersonal relationships and communication in the workplace through relational crafting, Immigration Office employees can develop a stronger affective commitment to organizational change that is needed to improve the quality of immigration services and responses to changes in the work environment.

Superficial Harmony Moderates the Influence of Public Service Motivation on Voice Behaviour of ASN Immigration Offices in East Java, Indonesia

The findings from the moderation analysis of superficial harmony regarding the impact of public service motivation on voice behaviour indicate a significant effect characterized by a negative coefficient. This suggests that superficial harmony diminishes the effect of public service motivation on voice behaviour within ASN Immigration Offices across East Java. Consequently, it can be inferred that in ASNs exhibiting high levels of superficial harmony, the role of public service motivation in enhancing voice behaviour is less pronounced. These results imply that ASN who have high superficial harmony, they have high pretence behaviour, are less honest in telling the truth about their performance even though the conditions are not

real, this will make the influence of public service motivation in encouraging strengthening voice behaviour will be weaker. The results of this study are in line with the results of the studies of X. Wang et al. (2022); Liu et al. (2015) and Nisar et al. (2020) that in employees with high superficial harmony, the influence of public service motivation in improving voice behaviour will be weaker. Superficial harmony refers to a condition where there appears to be harmony and calm in a work environment or organization, but in reality, there are disagreements, conflicts, or problems that are not expressed or hidden. In the context of immigration services, superficial harmony can refer to a situation where employees tend to refrain from voicing differences of opinion or problems that they actually have in order to maintain the appearance of harmony in the Immigration Office.

The theoretical logic that supports the argument that superficial harmony can weaken the influence of public service motivation on voice behaviour among Immigration Office employees is the theory of superficial harmony itself. Superficial harmony creates the impression that everything is running smoothly and harmoniously in the office, but in reality, disagreements or problems may be behind the scenes. Public service motivation will encourage employees to provide good service and participate in organizational improvement, but if differences of opinion or problems are not expressed because of concerns about disrupting superficial harmony, then public service motivation can be less effective (Hassan et al., 2021).

The weakening of the influence of public service motivation on voice behaviour can also be caused by the potential for resistance to change. In the context of the Immigration Office in general, change is needed to improve the quality of immigration services. However, if issues or differences of opinion are not expressed due to superficial harmony, then the potential for resistance to change can increase. Public service motivation can be a motivator to support changes that are oriented towards the public interest, but if the underlying issues are not addressed, then resistance will emerge. Superficial harmony is also often the result of an organizational culture that emphasizes disengagement or an emphasis on harmony alone. If the organizational culture restricts employees from voicing issues or differences of opinion, then this can inhibit the expression of public service motivation through voice behaviour (Hassan et al., 2021). Thus, in the context of public service employees such as at the Immigration Office, it is important to understand that creating an environment where issues and differences of opinion can be expressed safely is key to ensuring that public service motivation can be expressed through voice behaviour without the barriers caused by excessive superficial harmony.

Superficial Harmony Moderates the Influence of Relational Crafting on Voice Behaviour of ASN Immigration Offices in East Java, Indonesia

The results of the superficial harmony moderation analysis on the influence of relational crafting on voice behaviour showed a significant influence with a negative coefficient, so it was concluded that superficial harmony also weakened the influence of relational crafting on voice behaviour in ASN Immigration Offices throughout East Java, meaning that in ASN with high superficial harmony, the influence of relational crafting in increasing voice behaviour will be weaker. These results imply that ASN who have high superficial harmony, they have high

pretence behaviour, are less honest in telling the truth about their performance even though the conditions are not real, this will make the influence of relational crafting in encouraging increased voice behaviour will be weaker. The results of this study are in line with the results of the studies of Miao et al. (2020); Ibrahim & Salendu (2020) and Alzghoul et al. (2018) that in employees with high superficial harmony, the influence of relational crafting in increasing voice behaviour will be weaker. Superficial harmony refers to a situation where there is harmony or harmony in the work environment or organization, even though there are actually conflicts, differences of opinion, or problems that are not expressed openly. In the context of Immigration Office employees, superficial harmony can create pressure for individuals not to express disagreements or problems that may exist in an effort to maintain the appearance of harmony.

The theoretical logic that supports the argument that superficial harmony can weaken the influence of relational crafting on voice behaviour is explained by Hassan et al. (2021) that superficial harmony can create the impression that everything is going well and harmoniously in the work environment, even if there are actual disagreements or problems, while relational crafting involves employees' efforts to build and strengthen positive interpersonal relationships in the workplace. In a situation of strong superficial harmony, employees will be reluctant to express problems or differences of opinion to co-workers or leaders for fear that this will disrupt the appearance of harmony (Hassan et al., 2021).

Another reason that superficial harmony can weaken the influence of relational crafting on voice behaviour is because superficial harmony can inhibit open communication, as explained by Amabile et al. (2004) that excessive superficial harmony can inhibit open communication because employees may feel that expressing problems or differences of opinion can disrupt the existing harmonious atmosphere. In addition, if employees feel that expressing problems or differences of opinion is not in line with the expected superficial harmony, they tend to be reluctant to participate in voice behaviour. Hassan et al. (2021) added that in a situation of strong superficial harmony, the underlying problems or differences of opinion will not be revealed, which can result in the organization not being aware of the problem or the changes needed. Relational crafting that should be used to improve relationships and communication in the workplace can be hampered by the need to maintain the appearance of superficial harmony.

The implication is that in the context of ASN at the Immigration Office, it is important to create an environment where open communication and voice behaviour are encouraged, even if it involves expressing problems or differences of opinion. This can help overcome the negative effects of excessive superficial harmony and allow relational crafting to play a more effective role in improving voice behaviour in the workplace.

The Influence of Voice Behaviour on Affective Commitment to Change in ASN Immigration Offices throughout East Java, Indonesia

The findings from the SEM analysis indicate that the influence coefficient of voice behaviour on affective commitment to change is both positive and significant. Consequently, the research hypothesis asserting that voice behaviour significantly impacts affective commitment to change

within ASN Immigration Offices across East Java is validated. This suggests that an increase in voice behaviour correlates with a heightened affective commitment among ASN towards the transformation of public services. The results of this study are in line with the results of research by Akhmadi & Hendryadi (2022) and Munoz Medina et al. (2023) that high voice behaviour will strengthen employees' affective commitment to change.

The rationale behind the theory that establishes a positive correlation between voice behaviour and affective commitment to change within public services is grounded in the significance of open communication and active participation in the change process. Voice behaviour encompasses the actions of employees who express their opinions, offer feedback, or engage in the organizational change efforts. When employees are actively involved in the change initiatives, they perceive a sense of influence and control over the outcomes. Participation theory in decision-making posits that individuals are more committed when they are afforded the opportunity to engage in the processes that impact their roles and responsibilities, they tend to feel more involved and committed to the outcome of the decision (Locke & Schweiger, 1979). Eisenbeiss et al. (2008) explained that voice behaviour can result in recognition and appreciation from co-workers and leaders, especially if employee contributions are valued and implemented in organizational change. Reward and recognition theory suggest that positive rewards can increase individual commitment to the changes implemented. In the context of public services, voice behaviour has been shown to contribute to changes oriented towards the public interest which can strengthen employee affective commitment to the change because employees feel that they have an important role in improving public services (Locke & Schweiger, 1979; Eisenbeiss et al., 2008).

5. CONCLUSION

This study yields interesting findings regarding organizational dynamics. The results of the analysis show that Public Service Motivation plays a unique role in having its influence on Affective Commitment to Change not take place directly but has to go through Voice Behaviour as a full mediator. This seems to point out that high public service motivation needs to be translated first into active voice behaviour in order for it to increase commitment to change.

However, Relational Crafting has a more holistic impact. This variable may affect Affective Commitment to Change by both acting alone and using Voice Behaviour as a partial mediator. This fact indicates that the ability to establish and manage work relationships has a wider effect on attitudes toward organizational change. What is striking is the role of Superficial Harmony, which ends up weakening the impact of both Public Service Motivation and Relational Crafting on Voice Behaviour. This infers that superficial harmony actually can have a dampening effect on employees' positive expression and contribution in the organization. The findings of this study have meaningful implications for organizational management. First, organizations should provide more opportunities and encourage employee voice behaviour in order to increase the commitment to change, since the behaviour serves as an important bridge between public service motivation and change commitment. Second, developing relational craftsmanship deserves special attention by organizations due to its ability to affect change commitment both

directly and indirectly. Thirdly, superficial harmony in the organization must be foreseen by the management and reduced, since employee expression might be included in it. An organizational culture that encourages open and authentic communication is more recommended than superficial harmony.

These factors point out some limitations of this study and simultaneously provide opportunities for further research. The data used in this study are cross-sectional; hence, they cannot capture the dynamics of change over time. It is recommended that future studies be done using a longitudinal design to understand how the relationship between variables develops over time. Moreover, this study only focuses on superficial harmony as a moderator variable; therefore, further research is able to complement other moderator variables such as organizational culture, leadership styles, or the communication climate of the organization. Adding qualitative methods can also give a far greater understanding of the dynamics of voice behaviour within organizations.

References

- 1) Aini, N. (2002). Pengaruh job crafting terhadap kreativitas melalui work engagement sebagai variabel mediasi. *Jurnal Ilmu Manajemen*, 566–577. <https://doi.org/10.26740/jim.v10n2.p566-577>
- 2) Akhmadi, A., & Hendryadi, H. (2022). Islamic work ethics, komitmen afektif, dan perilaku suara karyawan: Sebuah studi pendahuluan. *SERAMBI: Jurnal Ekonomi Manajemen Dan Bisnis Islam*, 4(2), 151–164. <https://doi.org/10.36407/serambi.v4i2.751>
- 3) Ali, N., Hussain, A., Ali, A., Khan, I., & Ullah, M. (2020). *Impact of Job Crafting on Bankers' In-Role and Extra-Role Performance: Mediating Role of Organizational Commitment*.
- 4) Alzghoul, A., Elrehail, H., Emeagwali, O. L., & AlShboul, M. K. (2018). Knowledge management, workplace climate, creativity and performance: The role of authentic leadership. *Journal of Workplace Learning*, 30(8), 592–612. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JWL-12-2017-0111>
- 5) Amabile, T. M., Schatzel, E. A., Moneta, G. B., & Kramer, S. J. (2004). Leader behaviors and the work environment for creativity: Perceived leader support. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 15(1), 5–32. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.leaqua.2003.12.003>
- 6) Berg, J. M., Dutton, J. E., & Wrzesniewski, A. (2013). *Job crafting and meaningful work*. <https://doi.org/10.1037/14183-005>
- 7) Boyd, N. M., & Nowell, B. (2020). Sense of community, sense of community responsibility, organizational commitment and identification, and public service motivation: a simultaneous test of affective states on employee well-being and engagement in a public service work context. *Public Management Review*, 22(7), 1024–1050. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14719037.2020.1740301>
- 8) Bozeman, B., & Su, X. (2015). Public service motivation concepts and theory: A critique. *Public Administration Review*, 75(5), 700–710. <https://doi.org/10.1111/puar.12248>
- 9) Bright, L. (2021). Does Person Organization Fit and Person-Job Fit Mediate the Relationship between Public Service Motivation and Work Stress among US Federal Employees? *Administrative Sciences*, 11(2), 37. <https://doi.org/10.3390/admsci11020037>
- 10) Dyne, L. Van, Ang, S., & Botero, I. C. (2003). Conceptualizing employee silence and employee voice as multidimensional constructs. *Journal of Management Studies*, 40(6), 1359–1392. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-6486.00384>

- 11) Eisenbeiss, S. A., Van Knippenberg, D., & Boerner, S. (2008). Transformational leadership and team innovation: integrating team climate principles. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 93(6), 1438.
- 12) Hair, J. F. (2010). Black, Wc, Babin, Bj, & Anderson, Re (2010). *Multivariate Data Analysis*, 7, 77–95.
- 13) Hamid, Su., & Earlyanti, N. I. (2023). The influence of affective, cognitive and normative commitment on police performance. *International Journal of Social and Management Studies*, 4(1), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.5555/ijosmas.v4i1.262>
- 14) Hassan, H. A., Zhang, X., Ahmad, A. B., & Liu, B. (2021). Public service motivation and employee change-supportive intention: Utilizing the theory of planned behavior. *Public Personnel Management*, 50(2), 283–304. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0091026020934515>
- 15) Hayes, A. F. (2017). *Introduction to mediation, moderation, and conditional process analysis: A regression-based approach*. Guilford publications.
- 16) Herscovitch, L., & Meyer, J. P. (2002). Commitment to organizational change: extension of a three-component model. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 87(3), 474.
- 17) Ibrahim, M., & Salendu, A. (2020). Budaya Organisasi dan Voice Behavior: Peran Mediasi Kepribadian Proaktif pada Karyawan Lembaga Pemerintah. *Jurnal Diversita*, 6(2), 154–167. <https://doi.org/10.31289/diversita.v6i2.3676>
- 18) Kotlarsky, J., & Oshri, I. (2005). Social ties, knowledge sharing and successful collaboration in globally distributed system development projects. *European Journal of Information Systems*, 14(1), 37–48. <https://doi.org/10.1057/palgrave.ejis.3000520>
- 19) Li, N., Chiaburu, D. S., Kirkman, B. L., & Xie, Z. (2013). Spotlight on the followers: An examination of moderators of relationships between transformational leadership and subordinates' citizenship and taking charge. *Personnel Psychology*, 66(1), 225–260. <https://doi.org/10.1111/peps.12014>
- 20) Li, S., Meng, B., & Wang, Q. (2022). The double-edged sword effect of relational crafting on job well-being. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, 713737. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.713737>
- 21) Liao, C., Wayne, S. J., & Rousseau, D. M. (2016). Idiosyncratic deals in contemporary organizations: A qualitative and meta-analytical review. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 37, S9–S29. <https://doi.org/10.1002/job.1959>
- 22) Liu, S., Liao, J., & Wei, H. (2015). Authentic leadership and whistleblowing: Mediating roles of psychological safety and personal identification. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 131, 107–119. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-014-2271-z>
- 23) Locke, E. A., & Schweiger, D. M. (1979). *Participation in decision-making: One more look*. In BM Staw (Ed.), *Research in organizational behavior* (Vol. 1).
- 24) Meyer, J. P., & Herscovitch, L. (2001). Commitment in the workplace: Toward a general model. *Human Resource Management Review*, 11(3), 299–326. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1053-4822\(00\)00053-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1053-4822(00)00053-X)
- 25) Miao, R., Lu, L., Cao, Y., & Du, Q. (2020). The high-performance work system, employee voice, and innovative behavior: The moderating role of psychological safety. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(4), 1150. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17041150>
- 26) Munoz Medina, F., Lopez Bohle, S., Jiang, L., Chambel, M. J., & Ugarte, S. M. (2023). Qualitative job insecurity and voice behavior: Evaluation of the mediating effect of affective organizational commitment. *Economic and Industrial Democracy*, 44(4), 986–1006. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0143831X221101655>
- 27) Nisar, A., Abid, G., Elahi, N. S., Ahsan Athar, M., & Farooqi, S. (2020). Impact of compassion on voice behavior: A moderated mediation model. *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*, 6(4), 148. <https://doi.org/10.3390/joitmc6040148>

- 28) Oreg, S. (2006). Personality, context, and resistance to organizational change. *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*, 15(1), 73–101. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13594320500451247>
- 29) Perry, J. L., & Vandenberg, W. (2015). Public service motivation research: Achievements, challenges, and future directions. *Public Administration Review*, 75(5), 692–699. <https://doi.org/10.1111/puar.12430>
- 30) Qi, F., & Wang, W. (2018). Employee involvement, public service motivation, and perceived organizational performance: testing a new model. *International Review of Administrative Sciences*, 84(4), 746–764. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0020852316662531>
- 31) Ritz, A., Brewer, G. A., & Neumann, O. (2016). Public service motivation: A systematic literature review and outlook. *Public Administration Review*, 76(3), 414–426. <https://doi.org/10.1111/puar.12505>
- 32) Rofcanin, Y., Bakker, A. B., Berber, A., Gölgeci, I., & Las Heras, M. (2019). Relational job crafting: Exploring the role of employee motives with a weekly diary study. *Human Relations*, 72(4), 859–886. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0018726718779121>
- 33) Sarstedt, M., Ringle, C. M., & Hair, J. F. (2021). Partial least squares structural equation modeling. In *Handbook of market research* (pp. 587–632). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-57413-4_15
- 34) Saryono, S., Amin, S., & Yacob, S. (2022). Job Crafting Sebagai Faktor Mediasi Pada Kepribadian The Big Five Model Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai Polres Batanghari. *Jurnal Ilmu Manajemen Terapan*, 4(1), 117–130. <https://doi.org/10.31933/jimt.v4i1.1164>
- 35) Teo, S. T. T., Pick, D., Xerri, M., & Newton, C. (2016). Person–organization fit and public service motivation in the context of change. *Public Management Review*, 18(5), 740–762. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14719037.2015.1045016>
- 36) Tian, X., Liu, M., Jiao, Q., Wei, X., & Huang, R. (2022). Job crafting: A review of theoretical integration and application extension. *Journal of Human Resource Management*, 10(2), 38–48.
- 37) Wang, J. (2021). Research on the influence of dynamic work environment on employees' innovative performance in the post-epidemic era—the role of job crafting and voice behavior. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, 795218. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.795218>
- 38) Wang, X., Wang, M., & Xu, F. (2022). The role of synergistic interplay among proactive personality, leader creativity expectations, and role clarity in stimulating employee creativity. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, 699411. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.699411>
- 39) Yudiatmaja, W. E. (2019). How does public service motivation contribute to service orientation? Testing mediation models. *Otoritas: Jurnal Ilmu Pemerintahan*, 9(2), 162–178.
- 40) Yudiatmaja, W. E. (2020). Public service motivation and service quality of local government employees: A moderated mediation analysis. *Policy & Governance Review*, 5(1), 33–49. <https://doi.org/10.30589/pgr.v5i1.357>
- 41) Zhang, Z.-X., & Wei, X. (2017). Superficial harmony and conflict avoidance resulting from negative anticipation in the workplace. *Management and Organization Review*, 13(4), 795–820. <https://doi.org/10.1017/mor.2017.48>
- 42) Zhao, X., Lynch Jr, J. G., & Chen, Q. (2010). Reconsidering Baron and Kenny: Myths and truths about mediation analysis. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 37(2), 197–206. <https://doi.org/10.1086/651257>